

REFLECTION OF WEATHER AND CLIMATE FACTORS IN ROAD PROJECTS

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Master`s degree in On land transport system and their exploitation

Annotation. Throughout its service life, the road is under constant influence of vehicles and the external environment. It is subject to the active influence of numerous natural factors. These characteristics of the road must already be taken into account the design of the road to ensure that the roads built provide safe passage at the design speeds for the users over a long period time. Climatic factors have a large impact on the reliability and safe operation of the road. They are most influential in winter when meteorological conditions unfavourable for traffic during other seasons of the year are supplemented by snow drifts, winter slippery conditions and negative air temperatures.

Key words. Weather, temperature, technology, climate change, whicles, constructions, moisture, climate factors, roadway, slipperiness, service, traffic, metrological, renovation factors.

Climatic conditions affecting the serviceability of roads include temperature fluctuations, maximum and minimum temperatures, precipitation, evaporation conditions, wind direction and speed, snow cover thickness, frost depth etc. They limit the duration of the construction season and require special technologies for both road repair and maintenance in order to maintain the road's usable properties [1].

The impact of seasonal climate change leads to a reduction in the strength of road structures during the spring and consequently to limited axle loads for passing vehicles. The road is permanently affected by weather conditions in the form of precipitation, snowstorms, fog and icy deposits. As a result of these factors there is a gradual

deterioration of the structural elements of the road. The temperature regime is characterised by monthly average and extreme (maximum and minimum) air temperatures, dates and frequency of air temperature transitions through various limits of variation. It determines the length of the different seasons of the year in the road crossing area, maintenance processes, conditions and frequency of different types of winter slippage, the condition of the snow cover and the snow drifting of roads. If the area where the road passes is subject to sustained sub-zero temperatures during the winter months, there is less chance of icing on the road surface, but the snow becomes drier and more mobile and easily carried by the wind, hence more likely to be covered by snow drifts. In areas with frequent transitions through 0°C, there is an increased likelihood of slippery pavements. The temperature regime has an impact on all the usability properties of a road .

Wind also affects driving conditions; the most dangerous combination is high wind speeds and slippery surfaces, which can lead to a loss of vehicle stability when driving on open road sections. Wind conditions mainly determine how snow is transported in snowstorms. Winter precipitation includes snowfall, blizzards, fog, and liquid precipitation, leading to ice formation. Precipitation patterns determine processes such as snow drifts, snow and ice deposits on road surfaces as well as visibility distances. The negative impact of snow drifts on the serviceability of roads can be seen in the reduced capacity of roads due to reduced vehicle speeds. If a road is covered with snow, congestion and traffic interruptions can occur, the width of the carriageway changes, and the coefficient of traction between the wheel and the road surface decreases .

Winter precipitation often results in various types of winter slippery conditions, reducing the traction coefficient. The main danger when driving on slippery icy road surfaces is that, due to different road conditions, slippery conditions may not appear over the entire road, but rather in individual road sections. The driver is not always quick to adapt to new driving conditions. Slippery and snow drifts lead to significant

reductions in single vehicle speeds and traffic flows, consequently reducing road capacity and increasing the cost of transport. Precipitation, fogging and the formation of fog lead to reduced visibility. This also leads to a reduction in traffic speeds and road capacity, and the driver's perception of the road environment is impaired. With the increasing volume of traffic on the roads, the issue of road safety is attracting more and more attention. In the last decade, one of the basic principles of road safety has been the priority of life and health of citizens involved in road traffic over economic results of economic activity. This principle is taken into account in the development and approval of modern normative documents, in the design, construction and reconstruction of roads and in their repair and maintenance. When any activities are carried out on a road, the level of road safety should not be reduced. Weather and climatic factors have a direct impact on traffic safety, but the main elements of the road plan, longitudinal and cross-sectional profiles of roads are designed based on the traffic conditions for vehicles under reference weather conditions. Deviations of weather conditions from the reference values, as well as their variation by season of the year, lead to a reduction in traffic safety.

Weather and climate factors can be long-lasting (snow cover, sub-zero temperatures) or short-lived (fog, winter slippage). It is the short-term weather and climatic factors that have the greatest impact on the number and severity of road traffic accidents (crashes). On slippery surfaces, the braking distance increases, there is a threat of skidding the vehicle, which increases the likelihood of an accident .

Analysis shows that between 12 and 15% of the total number of accidents are caused by unfavourable road conditions. Of this number, about 50% of accidents occur in winter and are mainly caused by meteorological conditions resulting in reduced traction and limited visibility. Traffic safety is assessed by recording and analysing accidents that have occurred on the section of road to be serviced. The rules governing the recording of crashes prescribe that their causes, which are influenced by weather conditions, should be note low adhesive qualities of the pavement; narrowing of the

carriageway if there is snow on the road surface (if the width of the fully cleared carriageway is less than the values regulated by the regulations);

presence of snow banks at intersections at the same level in the visibility triangle area;

visibility restrictions due to weather conditions.

Seasonal crash rate schedules are used to assess the overall crash status of the road network being serviced. These allow the influence of weather and climate factors on road safety to be taken into account and estimate the change in traffic conditions during the different seasons of the year. Seasonal crash rates are plotted for summer, winter and transitional periods of the year. The influence of weather conditions on the change in the following traffic factors is taken into account:

- seasonal variations in traffic volume and composition;
- effectively used carriageway width due to snow deposits;
- Decreasing the width of the shoulders due to the formation of snow deposits on the shoulders;
- Limiting visibility on curves in the plan by snow banks created by roadside clearing of snow;
- Limited visibility on straight sections due to snowfall, fog and snowstorms;
- Lower width of the bridge carriageway compared to the roadway due to snow deposits and dirt pumps at the kerb or pavement;
- Change in visibility at level crossings due to snow banks on roadsides and at snow guards;
- Changing the number of lanes used on the carriageway due to snow deposits and muddy roadsides;
- Changing the adhesion coefficient on slippery surfaces.

The seasonal crash rate schedule is the main working document for assessing road safety conditions at different times of the year, on the basis of which specific safety improvement measures and deadlines are developed for different sections.

The value of the braking distance depends on the speed, the condition of the road surface, the serviceability of the brakes and other factors. For example, at a passenger car speed of 30 km/h, when braking sharply, the car will have a braking distance of 10 metres. At 60km/h, the braking distance will be 40m. So a twofold increase in speed will result in a fourfold increase in braking distance. The braking distance is much longer when braking on a slippery road (rain or snow). Of course, the braking distance is affected by the adhesion coefficient, which depends on the weather and can vary significantly depending on air temperature and precipitation.

In order to improve traffic safety during the winter period, a set of measures is provided to protect roads from snow drifts both in design and in maintenance. In order to ensure traffic safety in difficult weather conditions, the road service carries out works in accordance with the regulatory requirements for the level of maintenance.

In addition, special measures may be envisaged:

- timely information to drivers on the state of road travel;
- means of additional information for drivers on recommended driving regimes in difficult weather conditions (signs with changeable information, information boards, temporary road signs to be installed in winter).

In order to organise such work, regulations oblige road maintenance organisations to receive weather forecasts regularly and in a timely manner. Foreign experts estimate that a well-developed weather monitoring system on roads reduces accidents by 10-15%.

Consideration of local conditions allows for a more informed approach to design decisions. Consequently, when designing roads it is necessary to go beyond the general climate characteristic obtained by assigning the area adjacent to the route to the appropriate zone, and study the climatic elements with sufficient detail according to local meteorological stations .

Annual air temperature pattern - maximum, minimum and average monthly temperatures. Snow cover formation regime, duration of snow cover, average

beginning and end of steady snow cover, thickness of snow cover by month, frequency and intensity of snowstorms. Wind strength and direction, especially in winter when snowstorms and drifts can occur. Frost depth of the ground and its freezing and thawing regime. Temperature at the surface of the pavement and in its depth. Moisture evaporation conditions. Practical use of meteorological characteristics in road design :

It is necessary to go beyond a general climate characterisation obtained by assigning the route area to a certain zone, but to study the climatic elements in sufficient detail according to the local weather stations and to take them into account along with the general data for the respective road-climatic zones. The design of the road bed, pavements and other road structures takes into account the general weather and climatic characteristics of the area, the level of groundwater, the height of the snow cover, the depth of ground freezing, etc.

To determine the volume of surface runoff, the estimated flow rates of streams and side drains, data on annual precipitation and its distribution by month, its division into solid and liquid, the intensity and duration and frequency of rainfall, monthly and annual precipitation of different security levels are needed. The design of pavements, especially with organic-mineral mixtures, requires knowledge of the annual air temperature regime as well as the maximum, minimum and average monthly temperatures. The design of thermal and waterproofing interlayers is based on taking into account the depth of freezing of soils and structural layers of the pavement, their water-heat regime and the influence of atmospheric air temperature on the heating of the roadway surface. Wind forces create additional load, and therefore many load-bearing structures are calculated with this load in mind. The solution to the problem of selecting means of protecting a road against snow drifts is related to taking into account the snow and debris conditions. The design of a number of processes is related to the drying intensity of soils and various road construction materials. The organisation of surveying and construction work requires consideration of the length of daylight hours

and the weather patterns of the period of the year in question.

The design of roads and their system of operation takes into account microclimatic conditions.

Conclusion. Thus, almost all meteorological parameters can have an adverse impact on the serviceability of roads. The difficulty in predicting the pavement condition is that this impact is not fully accounted for by observational data from meteorological stations and posts. Winter maintenance of roads - a complex of measures to ensure safe and uninterrupted traffic on roads and artificial structures during the winter period, including protection of roads from snow drifts and avalanches, clearing of snow, prevention and elimination of winter slippage and ice. The greatest impact of weather and climatic phenomena (temperature, pressure, air humidity, precipitation, etc.) on the condition of the roadway (slipperiness, flatness, rutting, roll-on snow, etc.) is felt during the winter period of the year. Under such conditions, road safety deteriorates, the number of traffic accidents increases, and the speed of road transport declines, which leads to a drastic reduction of road capacity and increases the cost of transportation. Road network is a complex dynamic system consisting of interacting elements, subject to damage factors (transport, climate, aggressive external environment), counter-damage factors (repairs, maintenance), renovation factors (new construction, reconstruction), and other factors. The planning process in any dynamic system ends with.

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